

Kneeing ability of promising submergence-tolerant rice lines

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Kneeing ability is an important characteristic of rices grown in deepwater areas. We evaluated 11 promising submergence-tolerant lines and check variety CN540 for kneeing ability and yield performance in 1989 wet season.

Kneeing ability and grain yield of deepwater rice lines under 40-cm water. Pulla, West Godavari District, Andhra Pradesh, India, 1989.

Variety	Kneeing ability (score) ^a	Grain yield (t/ha)	
		With 40-cm water	With 80-cm water
PLA7007	1	3.0	2.1
PLA7044	1	1.9	0.8
PLA8574	1	3.2	2.2
PLA8575	1	2.5	1.1
PLA7020	3	2.7	1.4
PLA7111	3	1.9	0.6
PLA7121	3	3.3	1.9
CN540	3	2.5	0.8
PLA7051	5	2.5	0.9
PLA7052	5	2.3	0.7
PLA7056	5	4.1	1.8
PLA7112	5	2.7	1.5
LSD (0.05)		0.6	0.2

^a Standard evaluation system for rice.

Seeds were sown 11 Jun and seedlings transplanted 10 Jul. Water depth was maintained at about 2 cm. At 30 d after transplanting (DT), three plants/variety were pulled without damaging the root and placed horizontally on the soil. Kneeing ability was scored 8 d later. PLA7007, PLA7044, PLA8574, and PLA8575 scored 1 for kneeing ability (see table).

Water depth was increased to 80 cm from 40 DT. Yields were high only in PLA8574 and PLA7007; both had high scores for kneeing ability. □

Grain quality

Element content characteristics of 51 good quality brown rices

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We studied the content of 41 element characteristics of 51 good quality brown rices with high nutritional, cooking, or eating quality.

Seed from the CNRRI Rice Germplasm and Resource Department was sown in 1988. After threshing and dehulling, the brown rice was ground, mixed, and wet-digested with HNO₃-HClO₄. The digests were analyzed by inductively coupled plasma-atomic emission spectrometry using suitable reference standards.

Among the 41 elements, P was highest, and Sc lowest (see figure).

When we compared the contents of 15 elements of quality rice grown on the CNRRI farm with those of conventional brown rice from the Taihu River valley, the order queues were similar:

CNRRI farm:

P>K>Mg>Ca>Mn>Zn>Fe>Na>Al>Cu>Ni>Mo>V>Cr>Co

Taihu River:

P>K>Mg>Na>Ca>Mn>Zn>Al>Fe>Cu>Ni>Mo>V>Cr>Co

Results of *u* test indicate significantly higher (P<0.01) P, K, Mg, Ca, Zn, Fe, Mo,

Element contents of 51 brown rices.

Ni, Cr, and Co, but significantly lower Al, Na, and V for good quality rice than for conventional rice.

The average coefficient of variation (CV) of 41 elements is 67.6 ± 49.2%. □

Grain quality of some red rice genotypes

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The qualities of various red rice genotypes grown in different crops at Moncompu were determined at the Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack, India. Aruna showed minimum values for the hulling and milling percentages; Karthika expressed the maximum (see table).